

Equipment

The Dubcovsky's lab is well equipped for small scale sequencing and sequence analyses, biochemical research, DNA isolation, horizontal and vertical electrophoresis, PFGE, microsatellite analysis, and recombinant DNA manipulation. The laboratory has six -80 °C freezers, and ten -20°C freezers. We have two large refrigerated centrifuges and three minicentrifuges, a Diad PCR equipment and seven ABI9700 PCR machines. We have a Quantitative PCR ABI7000 equipment. TaqMan systems for wheat *Actin* and *Ubiquitin* endogenous controls have been already developed. We have all the equipment required for basic biochemical work including yeast-2-hybrid and EMSA assays. We share a water purification system, 384-well PCR equipment, gel image analysis, an automatic developer and dark room and a cold room.

For field drought studies we have a Sixth Sense LT300 Infrared Thermometer to measure canopy temperature and a full spectrum JAZ spectrometer, plus equipment to determine stomatal conductance and to measure soil moisture. Dr. Dubcovsky's breeding program has full access to planters, tractors and a dedicated Winterstiger combine.

Dr. Krasileva has full access to a 12 core, 64 Gb RAM workstation with both Mac OS and Unix operating systems. This workstation provides enough computational resources to complete proposed project.